

The Commonwealth of Nations: Interrogating Its Present Relevance and Exploring Its Strength for The Future in The Contemporary Globalised World

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Abstract:

This paper makes case for the interrogation of the Commonwealth of Nations in its present form as its relevance is being questioned in recent times. Its passivity in international fora and among its members states' affairs has led to the conclusion that it is no longer active, useful and not desirable as a platform for sovereign states in contemporary global system. The paper investigates why it has failed to perform in its present form in the international system and among its member states, what are responsible for such and how it can regain its past glory in the present time and ways to project its future for sustainable consolidation of the organisation. The paper posits to x-ray issue related to its non-relevance such as the organisation's objectives are not clearly stated, no permanent institutions within it except the secretariat established in 1965, no tangible budget to play international role, no lasting solutions to crisis among its members, notably Pakistan and India, the present and future status of the Queen of England as symbol of authority among member states is now under threats, occurrence of racial discrimination in British territories both home and abroad, still unable to curtail military incursion into politics in member states' internal affairs and no effective and management structure as Britain is no longer active player. As such, for it to be relevant in situating the organization to its rightful place in the international arena, it requires to have strong structures, rapid response to challenges affecting members states, end its docility in the global stage, assertive to conflict resolution , curtail human rights abuses, end sit-tight syndrome, terrorism and

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partner with member states in economic and other related areas. The paper makes use of secondary source to generate data for analysis while it adopts constitutional theory of international organizations as theoretical framework to mid-wife the study.

Keywords: Collective bargaining, colonial heritage, Commonwealth of Nations, Diplomacy, international system,

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Introduction

International organization like the Commonwealth of Nations seeks to better its member states' aspirations, objectives and to change their fortunes through collective agenda and resolutions for good ends to their respective citizens. It was formed by Britain to accommodate her colonized territories after their various independence from it and non-British territory like Rwanda and Mozambique under one platform for more economic, social, political, cultural and educational participation in global affairs to interact, interlink and integrate with one another for multilateral engagements, interdependence and partnership. The origin of the Commonwealth of Nations could be traced to Britain's desire to retain association of some overseas territories which would have some degree of self-government, but still under the British crown, such countries like: New Zealand, Canada, South Africa and some other former British colonies. The representatives of those former colonies met in 1926 at a conference to discuss matters of common interest interstate relationship and the desire of Britain to seek their consent before certain policies could be implemented by her. By 1931, the status of West Minister recognized the status of dominions and defined relations between the British crown and the dominions. Britain relinquished the power of managing their foreign affairs and their titles changed from colonies to dominions (Ikenwa, 2019:8; Anwar, 2016:3). As such, the Commonwealth of Nations emerged with the advance of British's internal constitutionalism complemented with the reform bills in the 19th century and the enlargement of the franchise in the United Kingdom, with the notion of a wider freedom for the dominions and territories of the crown. There is no ambiguity that the agitations of the American colonists in the revolution of 1776 brought critical impact on the thinking of British leaders (Kirby, 2010:5).

According to Rosenberg (2020) on the rebrand of the Commonwealth of Nations that:

In 1946, the word "British" was dropped and the organization became known as simply the Commonwealth of Nations. Australia and New Zealand adopted the statute in 1942 and 1947 respectively. With India's independence in 1947, the new country desired to become a Republic and not to adopt the monarchy as the head of state. The London declaration of 1949 modified the requirement that members must view the monarchy as their heads of state to require those countries, recognize the monarchy as simply the leader of the commonwealth. With the adjustment, additional countries joined the Commonwealth as they gained independence from the United Kingdom. So, today there are fifty-four members countries. Of fifty-four, thirty-three are republics such as India, Pakistan, Nigeria), five have their own monarchies (such as Brune, Darussalam), and sixteen are constitutional monarchies with the sovereign of the United Kingdom as the head of state (such as Canada and Australia). Although membership requires having been a former dependency of the United Kingdom or a dependency of a dependency, former Portuguese Colony-Mozambique became a member in 1995 under special circumstances and Rwanda in 2009 as well. (Rosenberg, 2020;6).

It is therefore to be noted that the Commonwealth of nations has brought useful insight into the realms of intergovernmental and non-governmental levels in member states' of human rights issues, economic and political related cases (Bourne, 2010:12). Essentially, it has been in a constant process of change since its establishment, facing many internal crises and challenges shaping its goals and purposes (Tolstukhina, 2014:6). The commonwealth is good for the understanding of freedom, patriotism and greater participation, dialogue and application of force, liberation and reliance. It is best understood if its dimensions are noted in the proper place. It is about dialogue, re-assessment and reform of the British world empire as the oldest international association (Torrent 2012,360)

According to Mcdougall(2018) that:

The commonwealth functions in contemporary international relations as a 'mini' version of the multilateralism encompassing issues of geopolitics, the global economy climate change, human rights and democracy while essentially an organization of developing countries, it also includes the united kingdom and the "old" Dominions. There is a particular focus on the role of small countries. Apart from its global role, the Commonwealth can be significant in regional contexts where there is some concentration of Commonwealth members. The Commonwealth also has a role as a context for civil society organizations (Mcdougall (2018:8)

Aims and objectives of Commonwealth of Nations

- i. To encourage scientific relations among member states.
- ii. To promote defence partnership among member states.
- iii. To invent channels of information exchange among member states.
- iv. To keep socio-cultural and sport connections among member states.
- v. To encourage educational assistance in the manner of scholarship, technical know-how for development.
- vi. To honor and safeguard the sovereignty and territorial integrity of member states (Ikenwa, 2019:12).

CHARACTERISTICS OF COMMONWEALTH OF NATIONS

Peculiar attributes can be noted as determining the Commonwealth of Nations which include the following:

1. It is a special association that does not originate from any treaty or formal agreement enforceable by law. According to Olusanya cited in Olaoye (2004) that:
... neither a league nor a federation. It does not exactly conform to any other organization. It is a voluntary association of members who for historical reasons shared to some degree common culture, common educational and legal system and common lingua franca, the English language. Membership is not compulsory and so any member can withdraw at will if she so desires (Olaoye, 2004:174).
2. Member states of the organisation independently co-operate in the search for progress, freedom liberty, and agree the Queen as the symbol of authority of the organisation and as the Head of the Commonwealth of Nations (Olaoye 2004:175)

3. Member states accept each others' citizens either as British subjects or as Commonwealth of Nations' citizens, or the two categories being separated from those of foreigners (Moodie, 1964:182)
4. The leaders of government of Commonwealth of Nations member states meet twice in special conferences called the Commonwealth of Nations Heads of government meeting (CHOGM). Member states use the nomenclature of High Commissioners as heads of their diplomatic missions abroad within the organization rather than using Ambassadorial concept at large except for non member states' diplomatic relations.
5. They usually give tariff preference to imports from member states.
6. Though, membership of Commonwealth of Nations was attached to the colonial past, it remains voluntary and withdrawal of membership is at the discretion of member states, likewise suspension of membership as it was done to Zimbabwe in 2003, Nigeria in 1995, the Gambia withdrawal in 2013 (Olaoye,2004:178)
7. It has no written constitution. Through member states have their own constitution that are connected by the common ideas and interests (Anwar, 2010:12)
8. The approved and official language spoken is English.
9. Member states must participate in the organization's games and sports activities.
10. Member states pay to the secretariat's funds.
11. There is partnership and cooperation among member states in the fields of Science and Technology, trade, medicine, law, finance and international politics. (Ikenwa, 2019:10). However, they differ in that they don't vote the same pattern at the United Nations, they differ on diplomatic matters, they have many internal languages spoken by their members, their dominant religious sects range from Islam to Christianity and member states belong to separate economic blocks (Gottschalk 2015:12)

CHARTER OF THE COMMONWEALTH OF NATIONS

Basically, the charter of Commonwealth of Nations embodied the principles of the organization as captured in the previous declaration drawn to exhibit its uniqueness in structure and membership voluntarily which non-existed before 2013. These are the following;

- i. **DEMOCRACY** to ensure that all member states embrace democratic principles in the internal political system as the best norm of governance and popular participation as prescribed by its charter.
- ii. **HUMAN RIGHTS** Commonwealth of Nations committed to the fulfillment of Universal Declaration of human rights and other similar human rights treaties respected in the exercise of internal affairs in the administration of justice in relations to citizens rights.
- iii. **INTERNATIONAL PEACE AND SECURITY** It has the strongest believe in the global peace and security of all people, nations and system and seek for protection and disarmament from the threats of war and destruction from both its member states and other relevant international organizations against piracy terrorism, human, drug trafficking and war.

- iv. TOLERANCE, RESPECT AND UNDERSTANDING. Member states have to tolerate, respect and have good understanding of one another in the conduct of their affairs towards the association/organization.
- v. FREEDOM OF ASSOCIATION
Among its cardinal point in the charter is the ability of member states to express themselves freely as sovereign countries, within the association on issues that bothers on their affairs.
- vi. SEPARATION OF POWERS
Regardless of the political system being practiced by member states, the charter of the organization gives approval for element of separation of powers in their governance/ programme to the organisation and for domestic purposes.
- vii. RULE OF LAW
Member states must entrench the principle of the rule of law in their working apparatus of governance as dictated by the organization.
- viii. GOOD GOVERNANCE
The organization's stand on good governance on member states is germane and necessary for popular participation and well being of the people of their various countries.
- ix. SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT
The organization's charter on sustainable development of member states are for the development of every sectors of structural growth and progress of their citizens and their countries in the political, economical and social dimension of human endeavors.
- x. Protecting the environment through internal security network, formidable structures and conducive atmosphere for member states to exercise their mandate over their subjects.
- OTHERS ARE;
- Access to health, education, food and shelter facilities.
 - Gender equality
 - Importance of young people in the Commonwealth of Nations principles
 - Recognition of the needs of small states
 - Recognition of the needs of the vulnerable states.
 - Role of the civil societies in member states (the Commonwealth, 2013:2)

Pre-requisite for membership of the Commonwealth of Nations

- i. Such a country must be ready to accept the British monarchy as the permanent Head of the association.
- ii. Member states must have attained their independence politically.
- iii. To accept other member states as equal and must not indulge in racism in any manner (Ikenwa, 2019:16)
- iv. Member states must have historical connections with British, directly as colonized territories under it and indirectly like Mozambique and Rwanda under special considerations.

PROBLEMS AND CHALLENGES OF COMMONWEALTH OF NATIONS

- i. No specific policy on migration
- ii. No common currency among member states
- iii. No power to enforce decision reached among member states

- iv. Member states' citizens no longer enjoy free movement within the organization.
- v. No formal rule unlike the United Nations Organization (UNO), European Union (EU) and the African Union (AU).
- vi. It's member states belonged to different and many similar international organization which resulted in divided loyalty and interest.
- vii. Secession is allow for any member states that
- viii. Most member states have been involved or still get involved in political instability in their various domestic affairs.
- ix. The issue of same sex and the right of women in critical sectors has not gone down well with the African and Asian member states of the Commonwealth of Nations (Eyssen, 2018:3).
- x. Issues of racism, bad governance and cultural disparities among member states (Lowings, 2010:8)
- xi. Ideological differences among member state towards the association.
- xii. It failed to challenge the power relations that undermine the commonwealth's principal democracy projects (Craggs, 2010;222)
- xiii. Brexist from the European union is a big challenge and threats to the future of the Commonwealth of Nations because the association is increasingly wearing out and Britain's global leadership has decreased greatly (Mcbride, 2020:7)

ACHIEVEMENT AND ACCOMPLISHMENT OF THE COMMONWEALTH OF NATIONS IN THE PAST

- I. Provision of educational development of students in member states. This gesture has been experienced for decades to citizens of member states in scholarships awards and free tuition programme (Pandor, 2009:680).
- II. Cooperation in terms of trade, investment security and technical areas of collaboration among member states.
- III. Provision of job opportunity to the citizens of member states in various capacities and levels.
- IV. Promotion of democratic principles, sending observers to monitor elections, granting aid to member states on training personnel for election.
- V. Promotion of games and sports to integrate sporting activities and opportunity among member states (Morton, 2017:6).

TABLE 1: LIST OF COMMONWEALTH NATIONS

S/N	COUNTRY/ STATE NAME	DATE OF INDEPENDENCE	Date of joining the Commonwealth	REMARK
1.	Antigua and Barbuda	1 st November, 1981	1 st November, 1981	—
2.	Australia	1 st November, 1981	1 st November, 1981	1901 independence was through the Australian federation while the actual independence came up in 1931 and was taken up in 1942.
3.	Bahamas	10 th July, 1973	10 July, 1973	—
4.	Bangladesh	26, March, 1971	18, April, 1972	—
5.	Barbados	30, November, 1966	30, November, 1966	—
6.	Belize	21, September, 1981	21, September, 1981	—
7.	Botswana	30, September, 1966	30, September, 1966	—
8.	Brunei	1, January, 1984	1, January, 1984	—
9.	Cameroon	1, January, 1960	13, November 1995	
10.	Canada	1, July, 1867	11, December, 1931	Adopted its own constitution and obtained sovereignty in 1982.
11.	Cyprus	16, August, 1960	13, March, 1961	—
12.	Dominica	3, November, 1978	3, November, 1978	-----
13.	Eswatini	6, September, 1986	6, September 1986	-----
14.	The Gambia	18, February, 1965	18, February, 1965	-----
15.	Ghana	6, March, 1957	6, march, 1957	

16.	Grenada	7, February, 1974	7, February, 1974	
17.	Guyana	26, May, 1966	26, May, 1966	-----
18.	India	15, August, 1947	15, August, 1947	-----
19.	Jamaica	6, August, 1962	6, August, 1962	-----
20.	Kenya	12, December, 1963	1, December, 1963	-----
21.	Kiribati	12, July, 1979	12, July, 1979	-----
22.	Lesotho	4, October, 1966	4, October, 1966	-----
23.	Malawi	6, July, 1964	6, July, 1964	-----
24.	Malaysia	31, August, 1957	16, September, 1963	-----
25.	Maldives	26, July, 1965	9, July, 1982	Special member until 1985.
26.	Malta	21, September, 1964	21, September, 1964	-----
27.	Mauritius	12, March, 1968	12, March, 1968	-----
28.	Mozambique	25, June, 1975	13, November, 1995	-----
29.	Namibia	21, March, 1990	21, March, 1990	-----
30.	Nauru	31, January, 1968	1, November, 1968	Special member until 2006.
31.	New Zealand	11, December, 1931	11, December, 1931	Granted independence in 1931 but ratified by New Zealand in 1947.
32.	Nigeria	1, October, 1960	1, October, 1960	Suspended in 1996 but reinstated in 2004.
33.	Pakistan	14, August, 1947	14, August, 1999	Left in 1972, re-joined in 1989, Suspended in 1999, reinstated in 2004, suspended again in 2007 and re-instated in 2008.
34.	Papua New Guinea	16, September, 1975	16, September, 1975	Self-government in 1973.
35.	Rwanda	1, July, 1962	29, November, 2009	Non-British Colony, but joined the Commonwealth in 2008
36.	Saint Kitts and Nevis	19, September, 1983	19, September, 1983	-----
37.	Saint Lucia	22, February, 1979	22, February, 1979	-----
38.	Saint Vincent and the Grenadines	27, October, 1979	27, October, 1979	Special member until June 1985.
39.	Samoa	29, June, 1976	28, August, 1970	Now Seychelles 29 June, 1976.
40.	Sierra-Leone	27, April, 1961	27, April, 1961	
41.	Singapore	9, August, 1965	15, October, 1965	Formerly part of Malaysia.

42.	Solomon islands	7, July, 1978	7, July, 1978	
43.	South Africa	10, May, 1910	11, December, 1931	Left in 1961, rejoined in 1994.
44.	Sri Lanka	4, February, 1948	4, February, 1948	Changed its name in 1972.
45.	Swaziland`	6, September, 1968	6, September, 1968	-----
46.	Tanzania	25, April, 1964	26, April, 1964	Merger of Tanganyika and Zanzibar
47.	Tonga	4, June, 1970	4, June, 1970	-----
48.	Trinidad and Tobago	31, August, 1962	31, August, 1962	-----
49.	Tuvalu	1, October, 1978	1, October, 1978	Special member until September, 2000.
50.	Uganda	9, October, 1962	9, October, 1962	
51.	united kingdom	1707	11, December, 1931	United Kingdom was adopted in 1801.
52.	Vanuatu	30, July, 1980	30, July, 1980	-----
53.	Zambia	24, October, 1964	24, October, 1964	-----
54.	Zimbabwe	18, April, 1980	1, October, 1980	Suspended 19, March, 2002. withdrew voluntarily on 7, December, 2003.

Notes:

- I. Fiji -1, October, 1970, left in 1987, rejoined in 1997, suspended on 6 June 2000, re-instated on 20, December, 2001, suspended again, 8 December, 2006, again suspended on 1 September, 2009.
- II. Ireland - one of the original Dominions at the period of the Statue of Westminster in 1931 left after passing Republic of Ireland Act in 18, April, 1949.

Source: Commonwealth Secretariat, 2010 and added information by the authors, 202.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The paper adopted constitutional theory of international organisations as the theoretical framework of the study. This theory explains the role of international organisations in international politics as key and central in the understanding of states' behaviours, actors and institutions. It examines the legitimacy of international organisations and their impacts in inter-states relations. It is the analysis of their legality and supremacy of supranational organisations as they are principal players in contemporary international governance. The theory is the application of constitutional principles in international organisations working for examining their principles, objectives and structures. The theory discusses states' interests, power and attitude within the context of international organisations for cooperation, collaboration and integration. The theory is both functional and social as it takes up their interplay to analyse the institutional background of international organizations, its membership, contractual basis, policy decisions mechanisms and the length to which non-

state actors and authorities aggregate binding collective decisions making. It guides both states and international organisations within and among the international system in institutional governance with problems solving capacities (Hooghe, Lenz & Marks, 2019:28; Qates, 2020:8; Bayeh, 2014:12; Lisa, 1998:744; Peters, 2008:17). Peters (2021) noted how constitutional theory of international organisations has in the past and now seeks to promote international order as he observed three waves of the theory beginning from the 1960s. According to Peters (2021) that:

Looking in more details at that ongoing third wave it identifies and seeks to pull out constitutional model which upscales the proto-democratic practices in international organisations by strengthening forums for participation and contestation, which rectifies to the north-south imbalances, inter-alia rooted in the colonial heritage by involving some actors from the global south, and which tackles the global question upfront (peters, 2021:652).

After the World War II, different representations in international organisations emerged through the means of official and unofficial setting that resolved divergent representational interests and objectives (Cogan, 2009:209). Among the writers and theorists of the theory include: Linos, K.S & Tom (2016); Lake, D. (2007); Teuber, G. & Tangit O.Q, (2018); Shinata, I. (2000); Peters, (1999); Mckinnon, D. (2005) and many others that opined on the theory which emphasized on the relevance and supremacy of international organisations to states, actors and institutions of governments across international system and from this theory, contending theories have emerged like neo-liberalism, neo-liberal institutionalism, functionalism, neo-functionalism and intergovernmentalism (Mitrany, 1944:358; Moore, 1963:20)

The linkage of the theory to the study reviews that Commonwealth of Nations as one of the international organisations in existence is guided by states' behaviour, actors and structures of its own, while the theory equally shapes the environment it operates and aggregates its conducts among member states. The merit of the theory to the study is that it has been successful in diminishing the costs of communication and exchange across international borders. It ensures equality among member states instead of hierarchy and embrace collective engagement and bargaining instead of exploitation. It ensures cooperation and collaboration rather than confluence of interests. Notwithstanding its merits, the theory has its shortcomings which include: (i.) It is just a rewarding power to the member states and it does not reflect current power dynamics. (ii.) It doubts the empirical reality of constitutionalization and call into question in the analytical value of constitutionalism, (iii.) It is normatively dangerous because it is anti-pluralism (Peters, 2008:6) (iv.) It is not sufficient enough being that it sets aside the sociality of governance as how the member states feel and think about the bond together in collective rule and highly practiced with reciprocity syndrome (v.) The British exist from the European union questioned the legitimacy of international organisations as constitutional problem. That is, the constitutional challenges of representation of the components unit of constitutional order, the collective subject in whose name authority is derived that narrates the legitimation of supranational authority (Qates, 2020:12; Linden & Jones, 2001:115; Mcdougall, 2018:13).

METHODOLOGY

The study made use of descriptive method and adopted secondary source in exploring the information relevant through the use of textbooks, journal papers, internet materials and governments bulletin were employed for the study.

WHY THE COMMONWEALTH OF NATIONS HAS NOT BEEN RELEVANT IN THE RECENT TIMES.

The Commonwealth of Nations is at cross-road to its existence and relevancy in recent times. To Shaw (2003) that “the commonwealth looks more at home or at least less out of place, in this neo-medieval vision of the present and likely future nature of international relations than it did in the realist paradigm”. As noticeable of the organisation, the following thematic issues represent mission areas that the organisation has not perform which makes it look irrelevant and passive to itself, member states and the international system:

- i. It does not relate to matters of (global regional) security except to promote the context for human security or regional basis to the foundation’s youth and professional activities (Shaw, 2003:735; Onyengo-Obbo, 2018:3).
- ii. It has not been active player in global peacekeeping missions interventions and mediations though visible in elections monitoring activities in member states.
- iii. Not relevant in playing confidence building role and rarely employ occasional appointments of special representatives of the secretary-General can feature rarely in some of the members states’ affairs.
- iv. Neither has it connected to regional economic blocks like Association of South East Asia nations (ASEAN), European Union (EU) North Atlantic Free Trade Area (NAFTA), African Union (AU) though; it affects mainly member states, but it has not utilize the avenues to progress its network or ideas for organisational integration
- v. Like other international organistions, it has been affected by new technologies. The internet has transformed it which makes information and communication more easily (without international organisation including Commonwealth of Nations) among member states, non-actors and citizens of the organization though, it has made the organisation to exist “virtually” and in reality for the new generation (Shaw, 2003:736).
- vi. It is not providing leadership position and will to crisis affecting member states, like India and Pakistan over the disputed land of Kashmir (Howden, 2009:4)
- vii. It is still unable to curtail and prevent military RULE (incursion) in government in member states internal affairs.
- viii. No defense or economic policy, no executive authority and no budget to play global role.
- ix. The old aged of the Queen account as a critical factor to lead the organisation is tending to slow action of its relevance (Elliot 2018:4).
- x. In recent times, few commonwealth countries have removed the Queen of England as their Head of state. State like Barbados did just that in 2022. The implication is that, it is frustrated and fed up with the system (BBC world service, 2022).
- xi. Health related problems is still a by challenge in member states health care system delivery. Such as cancer, river blindness, tuberculosis etc. (Collingridge, 2020:7; Chan, Rutler & Ashiry-Orelope, 2020:18).

- xii. Brexist policy towards the European Union has developed a corresponding effect in the Commonwealth of Nations where any member could exist itself without hesitation (Elkins, 2020:6)
- xiii. There is a widespread disinterest and disconnect within the organisation itself as often seen as extension of colonialism (Standall, 2014:2).

WAYS TO RESTORE ITS PAST GLORY THROUGH RELEVANCE OF THE PRESENT TIME TO THE FUTURE STRENGTH IN A CONTEMPORARY GLOBALISED WORLD.

Notwithstanding the Commonwealth of Nations' status and level in the recent past, it still stands to be reckoned with globally among other international organisations and institutions. It has a reputable past which can be brought to the present to midwife and shape its new path to the future with strength. It has performed and still relevant to the present time having survived the stormy wind of a crumbling association. Below are key and crucial areas that have restore its past glory: crucial

- i. Modernising its support from pre-occupation of political neo-colonialism to economic sufficiency. (Nagaraju & Amaresh, 2020:4)
- ii. Democratic consolidation and sustainable development to member states (morphy, 2021:4)
- iii. Articulating solidarity for member states in political, economic and social challenges.
- iv. It engages in collaboration with other international organisations for economic gains (Foreign and commonwealth office & Arkwright,2017:8)
- v. Support to member states in the field of education science, technology and research assistance. Regulate the affairs of members (Branwell, 2021:8)
- vi. Assisting of member states of third world origin on how to manage their natural resources in wealth creation (krishnarayan,2014:2; 13 kirby, 2010:14)
- vii. Writing their debts off for member states that are highly indebted (Ugwukah, 2014:5; Badamosi,2018:4)
- viii. It gives member states economic aid, development incentives, trade and investment access to higher education and new strategies for rules of engagement (Eyessen, 208:5; Donaldson, 2018:7)
- ix. It now provides an avenue for small countries with the organisation to feel equal with other member states (Mckeever, 2021; Chiriyankandath 2018:3).
- x. Many countries find it as a plus in gain, honor and influence to add the association to their portfolio. Rwanda and Mozambique are case in point to their former colonial masters, while the association has tried to retain the membership of the union (Gottschalk, 022:6)
- xi. Another prospect is studying commonwealth as a course of study which is being handled in the institute of Commonwealth studies at the University of London, London as the course has a role to play in world affairs, Members states and institution in related areas such as Climate change, analysis, preparing leaders, preparing details discussion, partnership among key players in societal problems, good governance and finding solutions to question on sustainable development (Salmon, 2021; 3). It encourages building a general aim on the global level and exploited chances for developing a Commonwealth consensus on critical issue in international meetings. Equally, building academic partnership to support nation-building, encouraging

multilateralism and facilitating opportunities for academics from countries of member states (salmon 2021,5)

EFFECTS OF GLOBALISATION ON THE COMMONWEALTH OF NATIONS.

As the world is now connected as a single community with varying degrees of issues, factors and concepts, the Commonwealth of nation is not left out as member states, institution and their people are dependent on one another for the society and institution to progress. The interdependence of states in a global system connect economically through the media and new information apparatus. Globalization means all the channels by which the populace are interconnected into one society. Commonwealth of nation has been able to combine economic, technological, political and socio cultural forces to the advantage of international trade, travel and tourism, transactional migration, education and other related areas among members states in which have increased investment, employment, and technology driven incentives (Inskumah, 2013:2)

ESSENTIALS OF CONSOLIDATING DEMOCRACY IN THE COMMONWEALTH OF NATIONS

The commonwealth of nations has been able to make democracy attractive, attainable and sustainable as virtually all member states are under democratic governments in one way or the other. The ingredient of democracy has been exhibited to the extent that any member states governing in variance to democracy is summarily suspended forthwith. It has created a specific culture of political and institutional engagement with democratic principles (crag, 2010:224) which places great value on development, democracy and peace as one of the core items contained in the charter of the association for member states that happened over time in the period towards constitutionalism (chowdhury & mahbub 2021;14). As such, Commonwealth of Nations has adopted the following elements as part of its principles:

- (i.) **Commitment to majority rules:** member states are expected to be committed to majority rules in their respective countries where popular and greater rules are decided by them by their people. Majority rule entails democratic practices which promotes pluralism and representation. This expands to territorial, functional and proportional representations in democratic governance (johari,2009:378; inskumsah 2013,6)
- (ii.) **Safeguarding of the rights of the few minorities.** Part of the collective principles of the Commonwealth is that it must ensure that member states protect the rights of the minority in heterogeneous societies like India, Pakistan, Nigeria, Malaysia and other members of the association. This is to ensure that the minority are safe and well catered for in decision making process (Mayall, 1988:390).
- (iii.) Agreement on the rule of law, equality of all people before the law of the land and the entrenchment of freedoms in member states domestic affairs.
- (iv.) The rights of the citizens to be prosecuted by competent judicial system without fear and favour. This will enhance robust judicial administration of justice in member states as noted by the Commonwealth of Nations. (Inkumsah, 2013:8).

CONCLUSION

The study has been able to analyse the Commonwealth of Nation's evolution, its challenges, characteristics and prospects for present and future relevance among member states, international system, non-state actors and institutions for sustainable development in the contemporary globalised world. It has promoted and still contribute to be reflective of

current analysis of policies for human development and security through member states. Its innovative recognition of and quick responses to a range of new issues from bad governance, corruption to civil society are informed by new contemporary perspectives in various related disciplines. As such, commonwealth has been able to survive the onslaught of colonial past for relevance and recognition to suggest, help to revive, redefine and sustain its contemporary global presence within its members, their citizens and the entire world at large.

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